

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF VARIOUS ROCK PHOSPHATES

Ingredients %	RP	MNP	MPS	MGP	MVLP	MRP	I(B)RP
Insoluble material	5.60	7.56	26.05	5.90	17.26	3.24	24.14
Al ₂ O ₃	1.42	23.05	23.92	25.51	33.90	31.26	18.96
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.28	0.25	0.24	0.25	0.32	0.96	12.17
CaO	44.98	32.15	17.00	16.45	15.50	11.38	9.81
MgO	0.08	0.09	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.35
P ₂ O ₅	27.18	15.46	10.34	30.17	11.97	30.72	15.60

RP - Rajasthan Phosphate,
 MNP - Mussorie Nodular Phosphorite,
 MPS - Mussorie Phosphorite Shale,
 MGP - Mussorie Granular Phosphorite,
 MRP - Mussorie Rock Phosphate,
 I(B)RP - Itagarh (Bihar) Rock Phosphate.

TABLE 2—RELEASE OF P₂O₅ (G/L) FROM ROCK PHOSPHATES IN WATER AFTER 24 HR AT 27°

Period After 24 hr	RP	MNP	MPS	MGP	MVLP	MRP	I(B)RP
	0.0052	0.0045	0.0012	0.0040	0.0009	0.0033	0.0025

TABLE 3—RELEASE OF P₂O₅ (G/L) FROM ROCK PHOSPHATES IN THE OXIDATIVE DEGRADATION OF COAL AT 27°

Period After	RP	MNP	MPS	MGP	MVLP	MRP	I(B)RP
2 hr	0.0110	0.0076	0.0023	0.0071	0.0017	0.0063	0.0048
4 hr	0.0137	0.0099	0.0035	0.0090	0.0030	0.0077	0.0060
6 hr	0.0163	0.0115	0.0047	0.0105	0.0043	0.0091	0.0077
8 hr	0.0223	0.0158	0.0083	0.0145	0.0075	0.0128	0.0115

permanganate in aqueous solution, the release increases to a marked extent. The colour of permanganate changes gradually from brown to colourless at the end of 8 hr showing thereby that the reduction occurs in a step wise process.

According to Banerjee⁷, for a typical low rank coal (C=79.2%), the optimum volume and concentration of permanganate solution for complete oxidation, i.e. when no coal particle is left over as residue, are 20.2 × 10⁻³ mole/litre and 225 ml/g of coal (dmf), respectively. The release of P₂O₅ from various rock phosphates shows a progressive increase with lapse of time. This is because of the fact that degradation of coal, which continues upto above 8 hr, produces more and more water soluble organic acids which help in the dissolution of increasing amount of phosphatic content.

During the course of this investigation it was noticed that after a few hours the solutions in all the systems became colloidal. This is because of the formation of finely divided hydrated manganese oxide as a result of the reduction of permanganate and intermediate formation of humic acid on account of degradation of coal. With lapse of time, further degradation of humic acid into benzene carboxylic acids occurs and the solution becomes clear.

Thus, the reactivity of Indian rock phosphates increases to an appreciable extent by the permanganate oxidation of coal.

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Triazolo [3, 4-b] [1, 3, 4] thiadiazoles

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LITERATURE records¹⁻³ the synthesis of some *s*-triazolo [3, 4-b] [1, 3, 4] thiadiazoles. One such synthesis is by George *et al*⁴ but the yields recorded are low. We report here the synthesis of some new *s*-triazolo [3, 4-b] [1, 3, 4] thiadiazoles by the modification of the above procedure, where very good yields of the compounds were obtained.

The compounds have been prepared by the condensation of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-*s*-triazole (I) with various aldehydes in the presence of sodium acetate. The structure (III) for these compounds finds support from analysis and pmr data. PMR* of IIIa in CDCl₃-DMSO-d₆ showed a doublet (3H) at 2.37 assignable to three methyl protons at position 6. It also showed a singlet (3H) at 3.20 assignable to three protons of methyl group at position 3. The signals due to one proton attached to C₅ and one proton attached to nitrogen overlapped and gave a broad signal at 5.20.

*Chemical shifts in δ (ppm).

Structure III finds further support from its insolubility in dil. NaOH solution.

- a, R = CH₃ -
 b, R = C₆H₅ -
 c, R = C₆H₄NO₂ - (3')
 d, R = CH₂O₂C₆H₄ - (3', 4')
 e, R = CH₂O₂C₆H₄NH₂ - (3', 4', 6')

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in liquid paraffin bath and are uncorrected. PMR spectra were recorded on Varian 360 60 MHz spectrometer. Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel.

4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-s-triazole (I): It was prepared starting from thio-carbohydrazide⁵ and excess of acetic acid according to the procedure described by Saikachi and Kanaoka⁶.

3,6-Dimethyl-5,6-dihydro-s-triazolo [3,4-b] [1,3,4]thiadiazole: A slow stream of dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through a chilled ethereal suspension (20 ml) of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-s-triazole (1.3 g; 0.01 mole) till it was saturated. Ether was decanted off completely and the residue was suspended in absolute ethanol (40 ml). To this, fused sodium acetate (0.90 g; 0.011 mole) and freshly distilled acetaldehyde (2.2 g; 0.05 mole) were added. The contents were refluxed over a steam bath under nitrogen atmosphere. The suspension started dissolving and a new solid separated out. Refluxing was continued for 4 hr when it was cooled. The separated solid was collected under suction and washed with water. Crystallisation from ethanol gave faint cream coloured long plates, m.p. 211°, yield 1.0 g (65%).

TABLE I—METHYL-5,6-DIHYDRO-S-TRIAZOLO [3, 4-b] [1, 3, 4] THIA DIAZOLES WITH SUBSTITUTIONS IN POSITION 6.

Sl. No.	R	Time taken for the reaction (hr)	m.p. °C	Yield %
a	CH ₃	4	211	65
b	C ₆ H ₅	4	203	75
c	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -(3')	8	227	60
d	CH ₂ O ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -(3', 4')	4	219	68
e	CH ₂ O ₂ C ₆ H ₄ NH ₂ -(3', 4', 6')	6	300	55

All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol. All compounds give consistent C, H and N analysis.

Similarly, other aldehydes, namely benzaldehyde, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, piperonal and *o*-amino piperonal were condensed with 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-*s*-triazole. The yield of these products, their m. p. and time required for the reaction are tabulated in Table 1. All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol. They also gave consistent carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analysis.

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Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of Oxazolones

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4-(2-Chlorophenylhydrazono)-3-methyl-5-isoxazolone is the only compound in the oxazolone and isoxazolone family of compounds which has been used against fungus¹. During our work on the synthesis and activity studies of some new heterocyclic compounds, we found that 2-phenyl-4-(α -methylbenzal)-5-oxazolones are quite active against fungus. This paper describes synthesis of some oxazolones and their activity against the fungi *Alternaria solani*, *Colletotrichum capsici* and *Choanephora cucurbitarum*.

2-Phenyl-4-(α -methylbenzal)-5-oxazolones (III) have been prepared by the reaction of azlactone, prepared *in situ* by the action of acetic anhydride on hippuric acid in presence of sodium acetate, with α -methylbenzalbenzylamines. The products are obtained probably by the elimination of benzylamine from the addition products of azlactone with corresponding imines. First step in the mechanism^{2,3} is the abstraction of a proton from the active methylene function of azlactone to give an enolate which undergoes electrophilic addition with the imines to yield unstable addition product (II). Subsequent